

DAMAGE INITIATION AND FAILURE PREDICTION OF ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINTS SUBJECTED TO THERMAL LOADING

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SUMMARY

Adhesive bonding is used extensively in aerospace applications as the primary attachment method due to its mass efficiency and high stiffness. While primary mechanical loads are often developed in the launch environment, significant thermal loading may occur during the mission and must be addressed. Conditions contributing to damage initiation of adhesively bonded joints are investigated herein.

Keywords: Adhesive Bonding, Thermal Survivability, Thermal Stress, Residual Stress, Composites, Delamination

BACKGROUND

Adhesively bonded joints represent a significant portion of structural attachments found in space hardware. Adhesive bonding is particularly beneficial when attaching dissimilar adherends such as metals and continuous fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP). While structural attachments incorporating adhesively bonded joints are prevalent and have been successful in numerous previous space missions, the significantly lower temperatures that will be required for future missions represent a major challenge. Furthermore, the design validation procedures for such bonded attachments typically rely heavily on coupon test data that includes the effects of environmental and cyclic conditions that the specific mission may encounter.

Based on these observations the motivation for this work is to equip the designer and structural analyst with a methodology for predicting adhesively bonded joint performance more reliably and with deeper insight

Failure Modes

It is widely recognized that stress concentrations arise near bondline termination zones when joints are subjected to either thermal or mechanical loading. High levels of shear and normal tensile stresses are present in these stress concentration zones, and the relative levels are dependent on joint geometry. Due to the relatively weak normal tensile capabilities of most composite laminates the local concentrations lead to failures often arising within the CFRP adherend near the bonded interface for configurations

that develop a relatively high level of normal stress. During mechanical loading the delaminations that develop in these highly stressed zones quickly propagate giving rise to catastrophic failure. However, during thermal loading local damages that develop may self-relieve the high localized stress states within a seemingly healthy joint.

Figure 1 Typical failure surfaces of CFRP-metal adhesively bonded joints.

EVALUATION OF DAMAGE INITIATION

A coupon-based evaluation is being performed as a step towards developing a general methodology for the prediction of damage initiation induced by thermal loading. Test coupons were loaded thermally to predefined levels followed by visual and ultrasonic inspection as well as mechanical loading.

The mechanical performance and predicted stress states of the thermally loaded coupons are being compared to that of pristine coupons of the same configuration. Failure surfaces are being investigated for signs of the location and extent of thermally induced damage. Strain energy release rates are computed numerically via the finite element method and are related to the damage zone developed in the coupons.

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